

FEATURES OF DIASTOLIC DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE SUFFERING FROM TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

According to epidemiological studies, 40–70% of patients with T2DM show signs of diastolic dysfunction even before the development of severe systolic failure. Myocardial relaxation disorders are associated with cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, interstitial fibrosis, accumulation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), microcirculation disorders, and endothelial dysfunction.

Given the high prevalence of combined pathology — ischaemic heart disease (IHD) and T2DM — studying the characteristics of diastolic dysfunction is important for prognosis and optimising treatment strategies.

Keywords: coronary heart disease, diabetes mellitus, diastolic dysfunction.

Introduction. Ischemic heart disease (IHD) combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a significant clinical problem, as the combination of these pathologies accelerates the progression of cardiovascular complications and increases the risk of heart failure [1–3]. Particular attention is paid to left ventricular (LV) diastolic dysfunction (DD), which often precedes the development of clinically significant heart failure and is associated with an unfavourable prognosis [4–6].

Chronic heart failure (CHF) remains one of the leading causes of disability and mortality in the population. In recent years, there has been a trend towards an increase in the proportion of patients with preserved left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) whose clinical picture is due to diastolic dysfunction. The prevalence of diastolic dysfunction is particularly high in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), which is associated with a complex of metabolic and structural changes in the myocardium.

According to epidemiological studies, 40–70% of patients with T2DM show signs of diastolic dysfunction even before the development of severe systolic failure (Zhao et al., 2020). Myocardial relaxation disorders are associated with cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, interstitial fibrosis, accumulation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), microcirculation disorders, and endothelial dysfunction.

Given the high prevalence of combined pathology — ischaemic heart disease (IHD) and T2DM — studying the characteristics of diastolic dysfunction is important for prognosis and optimising treatment strategies. [1, 2, 9, 10].

Materials and methods. The study included 115 patients diagnosed with coronary artery disease with stable angina pectoris of functional class II. All patients had previously undergone myocardial revascularisation procedures, which allowed us to form a fairly homogeneous sample for the analysis of diastolic dysfunction.

For ease of interpretation of the data obtained, patients were divided into several groups: The first group included 56 people suffering from ischaemic heart disease and simultaneously having a history of type 2 diabetes mellitus. All of them underwent myocardial revascularisation and at the time of examination were in a state of stable angina pectoris II FC.

The second group consisted of 59 patients with functional class II exertional angina pectoris who also underwent revascularisation but did not have concomitant diabetes mellitus.

As a control group, 20 practically healthy individuals were examined who had no clinical or instrumental signs of cardiovascular pathology at the time of inclusion in the study. This distribution allowed for a comparative analysis both within clinical subgroups and with conditionally healthy individuals.

Echocardiography was performed using tissue Doppler imaging. A Samsung Medison Accuvix V20 ultrasound machine (Korea) equipped with a sector probe with an operating frequency range of 2–4 MHz was used for diagnosis. The examination was performed in standard echocardiographic positions with data recording in M- and B-modes, as well as in pulse-wave and continuous-wave modes. The examination technique complied with the international recommendations of the American Society of Echocardiography (ASE) (Schiller N.B. et al., 1989), which ensures the reproducibility and comparability of results [5, 6].

Echocardiography was used to assess transmitral blood flow parameters, mitral valve annulus motion indices, and left ventricular filling velocity ratios in different phases of diastole. In addition, structural and geometric parameters of the heart were recorded, including end-volumes and myocardial mass index, which allowed for a comprehensive assessment of diastolic function.

Study results.

The analysis showed that patients with restrictive DD had higher E and E/A values, as well as shorter DT and IVRT intervals, reflecting severe LV filling abnormalities.

Table 2.

Clinical characteristics of patients with IHD without diabetes mellitus with different types of diastolic dysfunction

Index	Type of abnormal relaxation (n=34)	Pseudonormal type (n=14)
Duration disease, years	10,3±2,6	13,8±2,1
BP grade: 1 grade / 2 grade	27 (79,4%) / 7 (20,6%) [^]	0 / 14 (100%)
Dyslipidemia, n/%	30 (88%) [^]	13 (93%)
HbA1c, %	7,1±0,5 [^]	8,3±0,6
CHF, n/%	18 (53%) [^]	14 (100%)

Note: [^] – p<0.05 – differences between numerical values in groups I and II are statistically significant.

In patients with pseudonormal DD, IHD had a longer course, grade 2 hypertension was more common, HbA1c levels were higher, and chronic heart failure was more common.

Table 3.

Clinical characteristics of patients with ischaemic heart disease and diabetes mellitus with various types of diastolic dysfunction

Index	Abnormal relaxation (n=21)	Pseudonormal (n=15)	Restrictive (n=11)
DM duration, years	4,8±2,4	6,9±2,6	6,9±0,6 [^]
CHD duration, years	4,5±1,4	8,5±0,9	6,9±0,6 [^]
MI anamnesis, n/%	8 (38,1%) [^]	7 (46,7%)	10 (91%)
HbA1c (%)	6,8±0,6 [^]	7,4±0,5	8,5±0,3
Dyslipidemia, n/%	16 (76,2%)	12 (80%)	10 (91%) [^]
CHD (I–III ФК)	19 (90%)	15 (100%)	11 (100%, mostly HF IIIstage)

Note: [^] – p<0.05 – differences between groups are statistically significant.

Patients with restrictive type more often had a history of MI, higher HbA1c levels, and more severe CHF.

The analysis showed that types II and III DD were more frequently observed in LV hypertrophy, whereas type I predominated in concentric remodelling.

Table 5.

Comparative analysis of LVEDD and LVMI thickness in patients with diabetes mellitus with different types of LV diastolic function.

Index	Abnormal relaxation	Pseudonormal	Restrictive
Endothelium-dependent vasodilation a. Brachialis, %	4,2±0,8*	2,9±1,1	0,6±1,1 [°]
intima media Thickness of a. carotis communis, mm	1,02±0,04*	1,15±0,03	1,31±0,05 [°]
Atherosclerotic plaque, n/%	11 (52,4%)*	10 (66,7%)	10 (90,9%) [°]

Note: * – p<0.05 – differences between abnormal relaxation and pseudonormal type; [°] – p<0.05 – differences between restrictive type and others.

Correlation analysis revealed a significant association between diastolic dysfunction and the duration of IHD and SD2, HbA1c level, the presence of long-term arterial hypertension, and patient age. These factors should be taken into account when predicting the course of the disease. [3, 7].

Discussion. The results of the study confirmed that all patients with IHD have diastolic dysfunction, and the presence of T2DM shifts its structure towards more severe forms. Similar data are provided by Paulus & Tschope (2013), who noted the key role of endothelial dysfunction and interstitial fibrosis in diabetes. Our data are consistent with Solomon et al. (2012), who found that the progression of DD correlates with the duration of diabetes and HbA1c levels.

Thus, the combination of IHD and SD2 forms an unfavourable phenotype of CHF with preserved LVEF, characterised by severe diastolic dysfunction and an unfavourable prognosis. [3, 7].

The study convincingly showed that left ventricular diastolic dysfunction is a characteristic manifestation in patients with ischaemic heart disease. However, when IHD is combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus, these disorders are more pronounced and progressive. The presence of diabetes shifts the spectrum of diastolic changes towards more severe variants — pseudonormal and restrictive types, which indicates a violation of myocardial relaxation processes, an increase in its rigidity and an increase in end-diastolic pressure.

A significant factor in the severity of the disease is the duration of arterial hypertension and ischaemic heart disease. The established correlations confirm that restrictive type diastolic dysfunction is significantly more common in patients with a long history and a combination of several cardiovascular risk factors.

Metabolic changes characteristic of diabetes mellitus play a significant role. Chronic hyperglycaemia and insulin resistance contribute to the accumulation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), which alter the properties of the intercellular matrix, increase the number of collagen cross-links, and enhance the development of interstitial myocardial fibrosis. At the same time, the activation of intracellular signalling cascades, including protein kinase C- β , leads to damage and apoptosis of cardiomyocytes, which exacerbates the loss of myocardial elasticity and the progression of diastolic disorders.

Myocardial remodelling is an equally important link. In our study, more severe types of diastolic dysfunction prevailed in concentric and eccentric hypertrophy. This confirms that structural changes in the heart in response to chronic pressure or volume overload exacerbate the severity of diastolic dysfunction.

Endothelial dysfunction remains the leading pathogenetic mechanism. A decrease in endothelium-dependent vasodilation and thickening of the intima-media complex of the carotid arteries were significantly associated with worsening diastolic dysfunction. Thus, systemic vascular damage in the combination of diabetes mellitus and ischaemic heart disease is closely associated with increased myocardial stiffness and the development of chronic heart failure.

Inadequate control of diabetes mellitus also contributed to an increase in the severity of diastolic dysfunction. Higher HbA1c values were more frequently observed in patients with pseudonormal and restrictive types of DD, which emphasises the importance of strict control of carbohydrate metabolism to slow the progression of cardiovascular complications.

Overall, the results obtained allow us to conclude that the development of diastolic dysfunction in patients with IHD and type 2 diabetes is associated with a complex of factors: chronic myocardial ischaemia, prolonged exposure to arterial hypertension, fibrosis and remodelling, impaired microcirculation and endothelial function, as well as metabolic shifts caused by hyperglycaemia.

Thus, diastolic dysfunction in this category of patients is the result of the combined effects of mechanical overload, structural changes, and systemic metabolic and vascular changes.

The findings underscore the need for comprehensive management of patients with IHD and type 2 diabetes mellitus. In addition to standard cardiological therapy, special attention should be paid to early diagnosis of diastolic disorders, glycaemic control, correction of dyslipidaemia, treatment of arterial hypertension, and improvement of endothelial function. Only an integrated approach can slow the progression of heart failure and improve the prognosis in this category of patients.

In conclusion, it should be noted that diastolic dysfunction is detected in all patients with IHD, but its structure varies depending on the presence of T2DM.

When IHD and T2DM are combined, severe types of DD (pseudonormal and restrictive) are more likely to develop.

Diastolic dysfunction is associated with the duration of IHD, the duration of T2DM, HbA1c levels, and age.

Early diagnosis and correction of risk factors, including glycaemic and blood pressure control, are required to optimise patient management.

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